

Metaphors in Pakistan Politics: An Analysis of Nawaz Sharif's Speeches in General Election 2018

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Abstract

This paper aims at to analyze and interpret metaphors used by Nawaz Sharif (EX-PM) during general election (2018) campaign in his public speeches to shrewdly control the public behavior. The study also intent to present that a metaphor is a linguistic device can be used both for practical and deliberate motives. The study shows that metaphors are employed to help the democratic citizens to get a handle on various political problems and later to explain their usual approach to political matters. In political discourse the principle of mapping in which the source and target domains can also be utilized by the political leaders to achieve some rhetorical and persuasive purpose. Moreover, metaphors also expose the narrator's ideological points. The analysis shows that Ex-PM Nawaz Sharif makes wide use of JOURNEY metaphors, WAR metaphors, and HUMAN metaphors to persuade and manipulate the public. Researchers apply CMT model as theoretical framework to examine and interpret the political discourse (April to July-2018) of the prominent political leader of Pakistani, Muhammad Nawaz Sharif delivered before the General Election 2018.

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Introduction

Investigations of political debate have been shows that metaphors assume a huge part in public speeches, particularly political addresses. Lakoff (2008) contends that political leaders prefer metaphors in their speeches, to lay out the edge about the elector's opinion on specific issues. Edelman (1977) contends that metaphors are utilized to give the vindication, or inspiration to think or act in a particular way.

Both Lakoff and Johnson guarantee that the conceptual framework of our day to day life is formed and organized metaphorically "The essence of metaphor is to experience one kind of thing in terms of another" (George Lakoff, 1980, p. 5). According to Kovecses, "conceptual metaphor means that conceptual domain (A) is understood in conceptual domain (B) (Kovecses, 2002, p. 4)". Both source and target domain are the two conceptual domains. the first one is more clear, concrete and lucid in form; though, the later one is abstract, confounded, unique and hard to be perceived. Thompson (1996) claims that, We need metaphors to process, think and contemplate about political issues. For instance, POLITICS is JOURNEY is a metaphor that includes POLITICS as a target domain and JOURNEY as source domain. POLITICS as target domain can be figured out through individuals' involvement with an journey. The journey frame involves nation is traveler, politicians are vehicle, objective/terminus is turned into a leader, and hindrances, disappointment in political decision and so forth.

Political discourse depicts a unique role in forming public point of view and frame of mind, as a few politicians utilize their expository capacities and understandings to control and change the public viewpoint and mentalities. For turning into a viable political figure, an individual should be an persuasive speaker expecting to explore and appeal the crowd opinions and empathies. metaphors assume a very exceptional part in correspondence with others and thought since they convey, uncover and emphasis in making feeling of specific characteristics of our lives in various manners. Wilson (1990) argues that, metaphors utilized to approach conceptual public contentions used by politicians, to summon feelings, to fortify specific aims and to represent the picture adversely of the rival in the political correspondence.

Literature Review

In the twentieth century, metaphors remained both a propensity and chore for speech specialists and writers. These days, political figures all over the world are making use of metaphors in their speeches and political discourses to deliver their addresses more compelling. Their utilization additionally enable them to sufficiently appeal and convey their contents to the general population in a simple way (Mio, 1996). Political figures use metaphors to get a handle on society, culture, and governmental issues, yet a similar applies to all individuals, as

political issues and abstractions are frequently conveyed concretely to individuals who have political complexities. To think and discuss governmental problems and make them significant and meaningful, the people utilize metaphors to consider political issues with regards to new or intimate ideas (Bougher, 2012). As Ferrari (2007) proposes a framework for the analysis of metaphors, and inspected the ways the metaphors utilized in political discourse to impact, all the most unequivocally, convincing way to deal with to cease this battle against Iraq. He further argues, the usage of conceptual metaphors identify agony, fundamental question/conflict and the significant drives to determine the influencing issue in the contents. They recognized the persuading and the ideological foundations of the Mass Media speeches. In long run this examination of the metaphors depicts the impact of the metaphors that are used cognitively as a tool for the amalgam and establishing a proper system of discourse.

Moreover, Wilson (1990) opines that, illustrations are utilized to approach different political contentions, to vent feelings, to reinforce specific schemes and to address the picture adversely of the rival in the public correspondence. Mio (1997) declares that usage of metaphors is a powerful system in debate of a political nature as they let the citizens to grip the real essence of political debate as well as fitting into the basic concepts of data handling portrayals of public information on political issues. Grey (2000) argues that metaphors are simple and in general sense they are as easily perceived as we perceive our ordinary expressions. There is only one difficulty that we face in the understanding of metaphor and it is the cognition and clarification of it. Furthermore, Hu (2001) analyzed rhetorical expression in politics and at the same time exploring different political discourse under different circumstances, recognized some frameworks that are commonly used as rhetorical expression. These rhetoric strategies are broadly used as metaphors, metonymy, reiteration, parallelism and as well as genteelism. Additionally when it is utilized in political debate, it works like a direct antithesis or parallel to the contrary, has a persuasive impact in the conversation can accomplish in five ways, these are situational rhetoric, institutional rhetoric, the political knowledge of scattering of devices. He portrays that in different conditions, the political conversation can arrange into various types: the condition rhetoric, rhetoric of institution, antiphrasis and the principal rhetoric. Hence, political debates might be barely acknowledged out capably deprived of the utilization of rhetoric. Politics has deep influence and assume a huge part in our lives. Similarly, Fairclough (1989) argues that politics can be reduced to conflicts and efforts resulted in the language. Likewise, political debate and various types of this debate satisfy the politics, for instance, conferences, political talk, regulative conversations, social media and political exposure (Van Dijk, 1997). At last, the political issues and political discourse are blended in the territory of citizens, and both influence the exhibition of the hopefuls of the leaders and the audience of the political discourse that is a common man.

Lubna (2017) delineate that different metaphors have utilized and coordinated in Nawaz Sharif's argument and speeches in English as well as Urdu discourses that give conceptual metaphors to exhibit orators' reasoning and uncover basic depictions and political figures. The analysts' examination recognized and elaborated the target domain like political journey, political pledges, social and economic advancement. Thus, Nawaz Sharif firmly utilized the journey as source domain, building and light to inspire a picture of improvement by utilizing figurative speech.

Kittay (1987) expressed that metaphor is a figurative expression where we discuss one thing as though it were something else. It is an inescapable property of natural language. Subsequently, proper information on metaphor is fundamental to comprehend the political debate in light of the fact that a definitive point of politicians is to make their point of view reasonable to people in general. Thus, they use metaphors in their talks that can be effectively sensible to the audience. Also, Cen (2009) examines different political addresses of politicians from purely pragmatics perspectives. On the basis of the acceptance of the Grice's Cooperative Principle—he contends that the most elevated worth of the said Principle expects that the opponents in discussion adhere to the accompanying two guidelines: (1) never say what you accept that it is misleading or false; (2) never even express out loud whatever is missing adequate proof for, since political discourses should be based on truth, accordingly persuading, vigorous and compelling.

Ditmer (1977) contended that a word choice in our natural language is a figurative technique that conveys the message from a recognizable perspective, subsequently permitting politicians and interpreters of politics to transform from a more complicated and level of abstraction to a less complex and more tangible level. Al-Harashsheh (2013) illuminates a political discussion utilizing written or spoken communication in common language. Moreover, he also talks about verbal or non-verbal expressions as well that are applied in politics. He endeavors to explain, how political leaders inspire and communicate the feelings of the listeners and impact their attitudes and opinions. He differentiates political debate from any remaining sorts of talks, since it is intentional, valuable and directorial for a specific crowd of people. It is efficient and plentiful in the figurative sense of language, for example in metaphors and analogies. Hellsten (2002) albeit remarking on language of diplomacy expresses, that since the very starting point, metaphors are one of the most extraordinary component of the political talks and exchanges of information.

Yu (2008) concentrated on conceptual metaphors that are normally use in daily life and politics and their mutual relationship according to form and tradition. More than affirming that the body was perhaps the most universal

medium for the advancement of a culture of metaphors was recognized as an important channel for their selection. Likely, metaphors are made through our physical experiences/encounters, however fashioned by the comprehension of various customs and thus stayed well defined for culture. Yu expressed that face is an important portion of the human body for which the Chinese and the British are making many metaphors because it is the most definite portion of the body, by which we recognize and perceive individuals.

Mehdi (2012) has an alternate view. He criticizes the unnecessary utilization of figurative speech by Pakistani political leaders, arguing that “Pakistan’s political discourse is full of words, words, words, words, timeless tales of shaheeds and sacrifices”. Likewise, additionally he certifies that, it is challenging to take a choice assuming the outrageous utilization of figurative speech and the outright certainty on it is an innate part of our political tradition and our mind or on the other hand in the case that it is a special expression of a specific mindset of the main political stream of Pakistan during circumstances such as the present (Mehdi, 2012). In this way, the choice of different powerful and enticing techniques is not simply an opportunity, however it relies upon social and political viewpoints, as well as state of affairs.

Metaphor used by Nawaz Sharif

In General Election 2018 campaign, Nawaz Sharif fully utilized metaphors in his speeches and corner meetings to summon a visual picture of change. Future commitments, procedures, and difficulties that comprise of a more noteworthy measure of his target domain develop a portrayal of trust that is something similar to change, however involving the figurative language that draw starting around a source domain of TRAVEL, BATTLE, and PERSON metaphor.

They introduce their future strategies of anticipatory governance through political mottos, which fall under the class of conceptual metaphors, that is the source domain they regularly utilized is travel and “hope for change” is the target domain.

Nawaz Sharif’s Usage of Journey Metaphors

It is conspicuous to say that when one discusses a journey, he should have the course of the journey including the development towards the end of the line through a way to you. These kinds of ideas have frequently been utilized of depicting different ideas, for example, "life" and "political issues" and so on, despite the fact that JOURNEY and LIFE and POLITICS are very unique kinds of things, and accordingly engaged with two various kinds of activities. Nonetheless, it is a one of a kind component of human psyche to uncover the most dynamic thought or idea by to some degree organizing in the more substantial structure to extend it for more clarity through verbal articulations. Accordingly, the POLITICS is organized somewhat for figuring out with regards to JOURNEY metaphor. Edelman (1964) contended that the point of public discourse was not to find contemporary representation of metaphors, yet to arrange them in the eyes of common people, and to utilize straightforward and simple metaphors that are rehashed repeatedly over and over. Political leaders have over and again utilized these metaphors to reflect stowed away perspectives and have created metaphors or coordinated addresses.

The JOURNEY metaphor is used as a significant source domain which is a concrete word, of that each person mindful of, in the “JOURNEY”— the explorers through travelling and political figures are machineries that govern the country and it’s citizen will likewise have issues or inconveniences in the manner to triumph. In the result, when political leaders utilized 'POLITICS IS JOURNEY METAPHORS' in their language, the resulting conceptual metaphor emerges.

Term ‘Traveler’ uses for Pakistan or Pakistani citizen

Nawaz Sharif very regularly used 'POLITIC IS JOURNEY' metaphor in 2018 General Election discourses; where he treated journey as an important political source domain.

ایک قدم آگے اور دو قدم پیچھے جاتے رہے تو کیا ہوگا۔

One *forward-moving step* and two *backward steps* would not take us anyplace (Nawaz Sharif, 4 May, 2018).

ملک کو ترقی کے سفر پر ڈالنے کی سزا دی جا رہی ہے۔

We are being abused for embarking the country on the *journey* of development (Nawaz Sharif, 11 May, 2018).

آج ترقی کی رفتار 28 جولائی کے فیصلے سے پہلے جیسی نہیں ہے۔

Today the *pace of development* is not the same as it was before the decision taken on 28th July.

ہم نے کامیابی کا سفر انتہائی موثر انداز میں مکمل کیا ہے۔

We have completed our *journey* of success very effective manner (Nawaz Sharif, July 28, 2018).

مسلم لیگ دہائے جانے کے باوجود باقی تمام سیاسی جماعتوں/حزبوں سے آگے ہے۔

Despite being suppressed, the Muslim League is the only party which is moving ahead of all other (Nawaz Sharif, July 6, 2018).

ہم بلندیوں کی طرف غیر معمولی رفتار کے ساتھ سفر کر رہے تھے۔

We were *traveling* with extraordinary *speed* towards the heights (Nawaz Sharif, April 28, 2018).

Nawaz Sharif utilized journey metaphors very rigorous manner to give a positive impact to the public and he needs to utter that he has delivered a bunch of services to uphold the dignity of the state. He expresses that in the time of his regime Pakistan made a tremendous *progress* and was *growing quickly*. He utilized 'POLITICS IS JOURNEY' to convince common mind of the country: ہم نے کامیابی کا سفر انتہائی موثر انداز میں مکمل کیا ہے۔ In this

journey metaphor he intends to opine that, notwithstanding of numerous *deterrents* and *troubles* in our ways, we have effectively completed our journey with great competency. Additionally, that is what he says, we have consistently done the right administrations for public and never wandered off on our political journey. To win the public vote and their trust he made an attempt to appeal the public emotions and give them a positive image of himself. The journey metaphor of politics is widely used by him in various ways, this framework “POLITICS IS A JOURNEY” might involve “ECONOMIC ADVANCEMENT IS A JOURNEY”. Nawaz Sharif further said that: two or three different narratives (Govt) at the same time cannot run a country nor can be achieved the national goals. There must be one governing body: the one which is elected by the citizens (Dawn News, May 12th, 2018). Public representatives much of the time instrumentalize the language as a comprehension of the functional utilization of language that summons citizens to mutate the current truth on putting aside the agreement of ascendancy. Thus, based on CMT model, this will determine how and to what extent political leaders utilize the language precisely in a specific belief system or ideology. This will determine how and to what extent politicians use the language of a particular belief system or ideology. Hence, the above metaphorical representations showed that it was difficult for him (Sharif) of keeping up with the unavoidably lawful government, that obviously performs better than the other-particular government of the tyrants to take the country in the path of advancement. Pakistanis envision voyagers as lined up with comparative tests in Pakistan. In various metaphors and specially the “journey”, including their mapping incorporate the mariners and drivers versus voyagers, in case of rulers and Nawaz Sharif versus citizen.

Trial used as a “Journey” metaphor and “Economic Growth” used as a “Journey” metaphor

“Militant organizations’ are active. Call them non-state actors, should we allow them to cross the border and kill 150 people in Mumbai? Explain it to me. Why can’t we complete the trial?” — acitation to trial related to the Mumbai assaults that are still pending in the court of anti-terrorism in Rawalpindi (Sharif, May 12, 2018).

In the mentioned data that has been picked from the different discourses of Nawaz Sharif, in the general election 2018 campaign; while Nawaz Sharif, in day today life, concentrated on trial as “journey”: the journey to stop militant organizations had obstacles for him, and it was a difficult path, and full of obstacles, namely the judiciary trials. Subsequently, the dangerous road journey is treated as target domain while difficult path as source domain. There are layers, rolling rocks and floes, moreover travelers returning to the side of the road. In the real journey, travelers usually do not pose any threat to their fellow passengers, while in the political journey of the 2018 elections, Nawaz Sharif felt that establishment wants to cut of his long life political journey.

Referring to Pervez Musharraf (Ex-Army Chief), “The Constitution has to be supreme. There is no other way. Look, we put a dictator on trial; it had never been done before”. (Sharif, 2018)

Nawaz Sharif once again concentrated on his judicial trial and related it with the journey in daily life. General Pervez Musharraf endangered this journey of progress and prosperity—the military dictators always did this to the elected people. The trial was considered a strenuous journey. The journey had to overcome a lot of obstacles. It has become clear that political travel will now be extremely insecure for military dictators. However, in the past, he was lucky to be able to make a secure journey in the Pakistan politics. Nawaz was the main driver in the politics of Pakistan to make such a responsible tactical despot because of his unlawful journey in the political course. Subsequently, he viewed himself as the genuine overseer of the political way, since he was the principal leader in Pakistani politics to make a move against ill-conceived journey of the military on the path of political issues that currently Pakistan facing.

“In 2013, PML (N) took office while the country was in an *economic turmoil*. Massive unemployment had *plagued* the nation (Dawn, 9 May, 2018).

The previously mentioned figures are based on Nawaz Sharif's speech in the days of elections-2018; as Nawaz concentrated on the financial improvement such as a journey in reality. In Nawaz's regime there were obstacles in the financial journey of the state, the path was uneven, and subsequently there were gigantic possibilities of political and financial mishaps. Be that as it may, he was adequately lucky to arrive at in its objective securely as the other nations. In this manner Nawaz Sharif was fruitful to bust the economy in a similar balance of China and Russia. Thus, Nawaz Sharif proved to be effective in pushing the economy in a similar balance of Russia and China. In this way; he was extending himself as the best reasonable candidate to leadership of the country in the impending election-2018 campaign.

Source Domain: “JOURNEY”

In addition, previous record shows that Nawaz, as the upcoming prime ministerial candidate in coming election, seems to be preparing his story of hope through a source domain travelling with the “LIGHT and BUILDING” metaphors to appeal the citizens. The previously mentioned combination of various source domain is known as the home metaphor. Utilization of metaphors is the parable practice of a source domain to make sense of the essential parts of the other metaphor through mapping. As, it is clear in the greater part of Nawaz's discourse combined the different source domains with the fundamental source domain—“JOURNEY”; and they were found at the same time, hence, it is important to examination them in a form of one complete set.

Charteris-Black (2005) reviewed Churchill's speeches, finding how metaphors were repeatedly combined to increase persuasive results by integrating different source domains, such as:

“History with its *flickering lamp* stumbles along the trail of the past, trying to reconstruct its scenes, to revive its echoes, and *kindle with pale gleams* the passion of former days. What is the worth of all this? The only guide to a man in his conscious; the only shield to his memory is the rectitude and sincerity of his actions” (Winston S, 1940).

Mian Muhammad Nawaz Sharif, similar to Churchill, has also utilized the different source domain by combining them with one another as well as autonomously, during his last political race, which is as follows:

جمہورت کے روشن رہ پہ چلنے کے سوا ہمارے پاس کوئی راستہ نہیں، ہم پیچھے موڑ کر دیکھیں تو جا بہ جاتا ہی کہ وہ کھنڈر دیکھائی دیتے ہیں جو طویل مدتوں کے وجہ سے ہمارا مقدر ہو گئے۔ (Nawaz Sharif, 2016)

Literal translation: there is no other way for us to proceed ahead other than the enlightened way of a democracy; assuming that we think to see back (in history) we look the damage and obliteration to a great extent here and there that became our fate because of the long drawn out dictatorships (in the country).

In an interview with Dawn News before political gathering at Multan, Nawaz Sharif said, "The Constitution must be supreme. There is no other way. Look, we put a dictator on trial; it had never been done before" (Dawn, 12 May 2018). In this interview he mentioned Musharraf and further said that our workers didn't leave us but they were threaten and force to leave the party, and everyone knows that who did this. (Dawn, 12 May 2018)

Previously mentioned data related Nawaz Sharif political discourse, he has utilized the “JOURNEY” metaphor as source domain settled with “LIGHT, i.e., روشن رہ” [Enlightened way] that signifies democracy as a majority rule government. Here metaphor “DEMOCRACY IS A JOURNEY”, this journey resembles to a genuine process continuous traveling, Pakistanis are in *journey* in the country and the best way for them is *kindled path*, there are *lights*, so the best place for the stay and rest in is Pakistan. In this manner, Nawaz Sharif contrived to the electors that they ought to proceed with the journey. Assuming they will interrupt in so many ways to stop this journey. According to “STOPPING IS SCARY” metaphor, Military will try to create obstacles and decimation for them and this involvement in the governmental issues of Pakistan will effect the democratic process in the country. After a thorough examination of the available data discloses that in the past the military forces in the country derailed the smooth *process of democracy*; and hence, everyday person in the country *confronted* so may *difficulties*. The nation was pushed maneuvered into the back foot. The ordinary people in the nation were disregarded and very few are benefited. Furthermore, there was an exclusive show of a single performer in the country, consequently which ceased the journey of the ordinary man's life. philosophical investigation of the information adjusts that the *smooth and peaceful journey* of a vote based system is inescapable for the *advancement and development* of Pakistan.

The utility of METAPHORS in political debate such as of JOURNEY is to show adjustments and actuating's insight of creative beginning in the politics (Koteyco, 2009). “Life is journey” enables us to understand the utility of other journey throughout our everyday life. In this manner, “JOURNEY METAPHOR” is the most convincing source domain among all the figurative speech to perceive the target domain based on our day to day observations. (Lakoff and Johnson, 1989).

Nawaz Sharif uses Metaphors “Politics Is War”

After a thorough analysis of Nawaz Sharif speeches that he delivered during 2018 election campaign which consist the war metaphor, clearly the concrete domain of the war is for the most part utilized in the abstract domain of politics. Though, the people think and talk as for war, something significant that emerges to mind is the image of the more than one military force battling each other to survive or overcome a land. Consequently, the principal reason for a conflict of assault is to harm of the foe. Subsequently, when one of the rival's starts going after and initiate the war, it will go after other in reverse, at long last in the fight; one of the gatherings achieves the triumph while the other one is defeated. In the politics it is feasible to apply a similar expectation with the same intention; politics is totally different from physical interaction, then again of a persuasive war wherein one of the groups needs to be a champion. The ideological groups contrast in its viewpoints and political undertakings and when one of the party might go after the reasonable answer of the second party will be the counter offensive.

Politicians are Warriors

The dispute among the politicians could be seen as battle in the front line and consequently political leaders can be viewed as *heroes* and *fighter* of great war against each other. Further, while complicated in a discussion, the politicians as government officials battle for their ideologies, purposes and constituents. Consequently, the terms like *war/battle*, *maintain*, *triumph* and *achievement* could be for the most part utilized in metaphorical discourses of legislative and political issues, which could be figured out in the succeeding articulations.

میں نے ان حالات کا پہلے بھی مقابلہ کیا ہے یہ مجھے خوفزدہ نہیں کر سکتے۔

I have *confronted* such circumstances even before they cannot be *frighten* me at all. (Nawaz Sharif, April 28, 2018)

عمران کی لڑائی نواز شریف سے ہے، ہتھیار زرداری کے سامنے ڈال دئیے۔

Although Imran's *fight* is with Nawaz Sharif, he has *laid down* (his) arms in front of Zardari.

ہم نے دہشتگردی کے آنکھوں میں آنکھیں ڈال کر مقابلہ کیا۔

We bravely *fought* against *terrorism* with determination and squinting.

ہم نے ملک سے اندھیرے مٹا کر اجالے لے آئے ہیں۔

We have removed darkness from the country and brought light/success. (Nawaz Sharif, May 14, 2018).

In Pakistani politics, regarding source domain, WAR is extremely common metaphor. they help common citizens to access to political issues easily like politicians have information related to war.

Political Voting is AWar on a Battlefield

The concept of war and fight is utilized figuratively in each contention and debates of human. After this metaphorical implication, that's what Lakoff and Johnson guarantee, reasoning is somewhat organized, comprehended, performed, and talked with regards to conflict (Lakoff and Johnson 1980). The concept of democratic process can grasp through the individual's experience in a conflict. Through the domain of war each political party intellectualized the process of voting in the country. This metaphor of conflict has always been utilized as a real conflict among the parties and language and reasoning are conceptualized as *weapons* in the *conflict*. In political voting system the political rivals are fighting against each other as a *combat* in real war. Thusly, "war metaphors" appear to be present in the political race. The political talk delights regularly utilized words like *battle*, *loss*, *gain*, *stick to and stay alive*. Moreover, some of political forerunners in their addresses utilized the word *assault*, *rout* or *battles*. Similarly Nawaz Sharif as often as possible use 'POLITICS IS WAR METAPHORS' in his overall political racing during election 2018. Nawaz Sharif said:

کیا ہم صرف دیکھتے رہیں گے یا مقابلہ بھی کریں گے؟

Are we just going to watch? Or we will *fight* too?

اگر ہمیں مقابلہ نہیں کرنا، تو ہمیں عوام کی نمائندگی کا کوئی حق نہیں۔

If we do not *compete*, we have no right to *represent* the nation (Nawaz Sharif, April 28, 2018)-

ہمارا مقابلہ عمران یا زرداری سے نہیں ہمارا مقابلہ کسی اور سے ہے۔

Our *competition* is not with Imran or Zardari but our competition is with other than them (Nawaz Sharif, April 30, 2018).

"If there really was a *mahaz* (*front*), then why did it last only two days?" (Dawn, May 12, 2018)

Previously mentioned information in hand discloses that Nawaz Sharif utilizes the term "war"—which signifies a fight to win in the political arena/general election. This electoral process was treated as a challenge like a genuine combat in a battle. In this process of conceptualization, Language is used as weapon that refers to a verbal combat among the fighters. Hence, the goal of this fighting is to defeat one another in the coming election(war) via the addresses to scrounge up favor of the citizens. Likewise, competition between two candidates in this democratic process is by all accounts very brutal. At the point when Nawaz Sharif tended to his electoral addresses, he endeavored to utilize words to victory over his contrary party. Hence, from the above illustrations it is obvious that legislative/political issues and war are two very distinct ideas however as a conceptual metaphor one might see a conceptual mapping between them, that is, the idea of "war" as SOURCE DOMAIN is mapping on to the idea of politics as TARGET DOMAIN. Consequently, the ontological correspondence, for instance, The perceptually dangerous WAR property of the source domain is mapped to the perceptually dangerous and unsafe property of POLITICS of the target domain. This sort of mapping shows the commonality of the concepts of war and politics in order to present a very abstract idea in a very concrete structural frame.

Triumph in War is triumph over the rival party

Election is always treated as a war or combat among the various political opponents and parties. In that sense, it is pretty much clear that with all the things involved in elections, such as *policies*, *contestants*, *strategies*, *missions and measurements*, these war terms are easy to understand. Ordinary people will easily draw parallels between both *politics* as "source domain" and *war* as "target domain".

اللہ ہمیں اس جنگ میں ضرور کامیاب کرے گا۔

Allah will definitely make us successful in this war (Nawaz Sharif, April 28, 2018).

انشاء اللہ فتح ہماری مسلم لیگ (ن) کے شیر کو ہی ہوگی۔

If Allah Almighty wills, the lion/tiger of Muslim League (N) will be victorious.

کیا عمران خان نواز شریف کے شیروں کا مقابلہ کر سکے گا؟

Will Imran Khan be able to fight the lions of Nawaz Sharif? (Nawaz Sharif, May 14, 2018)

The "conceptual metaphors" of war and their figurative articulation used during the election campaign is to pass the message to the common man of the country that casting a vote is a serious business that requires sincere, urgent and rigorous action.

Political Strategies Are Military Strategies

Politicians metaphorically and figuratively symbolized political policies into army policies. "In warfare, you need space to align your troops, room to maneuver. The more space you have, the more intricate your strategy can be. But sometimes it is better to overwhelm the enemy, giving them no time to think or react" (Greene, 2003, p. 212). Absolutely, this is the very thing politicians are guaranteed of when they should fight against their

rivals. Furthermore, they need to have a trump card to safeguard their face and get benefitted. Obviously, politicians sometimes acknowledge *strategies* firmly connected with *war strategies* to overcome the foes.

آئندہ انتخابات حکومت کی پانچ سالہ کارکردگی پر لڑوں گا۔

I will compete the upcoming election owing to five years' performance of my government (Nawaz Sharif, April 30, 2018).

Nawaz Sharif's Usage of Human Metaphors

The usage of Human metaphor is a sort of ontological representation of metaphor which is exceptionally normal in political debates (Lakoff, 2004, 2008; Charteris-Black, 2005; Chilton, 2004). The individual's attributes and conditions that one goes over in day to day life or political basics are involved to political problem. In a particular setup, different individuals have specific guidelines, values, and lifestyle, have encounters of different infections, are solid or feeble. These characteristics, perspectives, guidelines, happenings, and so forth could produce positive or negative connections among them, since these characteristics are a fundamental part of daily routine life. Through this positive or negative connection, it personifies and highlights political problems. Such as;

Dispositional Qualities

These qualities used as first conceptual mapping, which represents that the state, like a person, has temperaments or disposition. Such as,

اپنے ملک کی تقدیر کو بدلنا ہے۔

We need to change the destiny of our country.

ہم یہ جو گزری ہے وہ اس پاکستان پر نہیں گزرنی چاہیے۔

Pakistan should not suffer what we have suffered.

کیا پاکستان اس طرح کے حالات برداشت کر سکتا ہے۔

Can Pakistan afford to suffer such kinds of situation? (Nawaz Sharif, April 28, 2018).

2013 سے 2018 کا پاکستان مختلف ہے۔

The Pakistan of 2018 is different than the Pakistan of 2013.

عبادت سمجھ کر پاکستان کی خدمت کر رہے ہیں۔

We are serving Pakistan as worship.

انجام تک پہنچے۔ اللہ اس مملکت (پاکستان) کی ہمیشہ حفاظت فرمائے اور اس میں رکاوٹیں کھڑی کرنے والوں کو

May Allah guard this state (Pakistan) forever, and chastise those who create hurdles for it. (Nawaz Sharif, July 6, 2018)

پاکستان کاموجودہ صورت حال آپ کے سامنے ہیں۔

The current Pakistan's conditions are in front of you (Nawaz Sharif, April 30, 2018).

پاکستان کے بچوں کا مستقبل میری اولین ترجیح ہے۔

The future of Pakistan's children is my foremost priority (Nawaz Sharif, May 31, 2018)

ملک کی مفاد کو ذاتی مفاد کے لئے قربان کیا جا رہا ہے۔

The interest of the country is being sacrificed for personal interest (Nawaz Sharif, April 28, 2018).

ہم مل کر پاکستان کو رسوائی اور تنزلی سے بچائیں گے۔

Together we have to protect Pakistan from disgrace and downcast state (Nawaz Sharif, May 4, 2018).

to describe The Former Prime Minister (Nawaz Sharif) used metaphorical expressions such as Pakistan a person and tried to vents the emotion of responsibility of public.

(Together we have to protect Pakistan from disgrace and downcast state). Nawaz Sharif further argues that Imran Khan is definitely an arrogant man and has no leadership qualities to lead the country. he will destroy the Pakistan's honor in the whole world. It is obligatory upon us to safeguard our nation together. You people remember the day that we brought Pakistan out of darkness by working hard day and night and we tried our best to improve it while these people do not want it because it is against their interest. they see their own personal advantages (Dawn Newspaper, June seventh, 2018). Utilizing this large number of metaphors in his speeches he needs to demonstrate that, he is an extraordinary and legit politician, he has consistently held Pakistan's head high with satisfaction. What's more, he needs to get the votes of the people by saying that he is the most appropriate and relevant person for Pakistan.

Health and Strength Metaphors

These metaphors are used to specify the economic condition of the state. The healthier and strong state is the one which is economically stable. The economic stability is the sign of a healthy state which plays a pivotal role in the progress of a state. A strong and healthy economy is required for a strong state.

معشیت مضبوط، سرمایہ کاری میں اضافہ ہو رہا تھا۔

Economy was strong and investment was increasing (Nawaz Sharif, April 28, 2018).

The above metaphors, Nawaz Sharif depicted very negative image of Pakistan's economy. According to him, the country's economy was strong during his regime and investments were on its hike. People had trust in us.

Moreover, the thorough analysis of the data related to human metaphor shows that he used such metaphors in his speeches, as Nawaz Sharif (2018) argued! "ووٹ کو عزت دو!" "ووٹ کو عزت دو!" "ووٹ کو عزت دو!"

In 2018, this sentence "ووٹ کو عزت دو" (give *dignity* to vote) becomes the political narrative of Nawaz Sharif's political party (PML-N). Before election they were heard in public gatherings, rallies and talk shows; by supporters as they planned to make their choice on election day to cast vote in the favor of their leaders; and large numbers of people had accumulated in Lahore on 13th July to get the entry of their political leader's. Such words were inscribed on banners by followers; some followers painted it on their backs. Chaudhry Kashif, as devotee and die hard supporter, says that he didn't join PML-N as worker, since his military days he and his entire family upheld Nawaz Sharif. This slogan "ووٹ کو عزت دو" (give *dignity* to vote) become popular is because people know that progress is not possible without civil supremacy. During the election campaign process, such types slogans and songs are used to convince the nation to cast vote for them. In the democratic process where people have to be persuaded to go out and vote on election day, mottos capture feeling and commitments to the nation; politicians reverberate the determination of voters, they also emulate and address the issues as it arises by them at that time. Some display their party insignia, while others follow to form alliances with the social, religious or political lines. Almost all create alternate roles around their leadership. Many neglect to get on, while a couple get through lengthy after a single mission ends.

After a thorough analysis of the data in hand shows that dignity is used as source domain which mapped vote as target domain. Here the term *vote* is treated as *human and personified* while *dignity* is treated as *human's* characteristic. Hence, everyone has to respect the vote.

Conclusion

The analysis of the public addresses of Nawaz Sharif, the prominent political leader of Pakistan imparted that the semantic control, persuasion, influence, and simplification are essential for the political talk in Pakistan. Ex-PM Nawaz Sharif in 2018 General-Election publicize his essential political slogan and uncover shortcoming of the rival to gain the power. Moreover, he is very genius and well aware of the linguistic manipulation tactics and use in extreme to gain public attention and sympathy. In times of election politicians used metaphors in order to make the abstract political concept clear and understandable and also to make their speeches more powerful and persuasive. This research examined and interpreted three metaphors ("POLITICS is JOURNEY", "POLITICS is WAR", and "HUMAN METAPHOR") used by the prominent political figure of Pakistan Muhammad Nawaz Sharif of the General-Election 2018 and Lakoff and Johnson's CMT model was applied to analyze metaphors used by him.

All through the review, there are numerous precise metaphors, for example, in JOURNEY metaphors: POLITICIANS are treated as TRAVELERS, and ROUTE is a POLITICAL SCHEMATA. In PERSONIFICATION metaphors: DISPOSITIONS are ATTRIBUTES, "GROWTH IS DEVELOPMENT" and "WELL-BEING and POWER are ECONOMIC STABILITY and AUTHORITY". In WAR representations; "POLITICIANS are SOLDIERS, POLITICIANS are FIGHTERS", "A POLITICAL VOTING is a BATTLE" in the arena and VICTORY in WAR is a SUCCESS over the OPPONENT to win the upcoming election.

Thus the more frequently used metaphors in 2018 General-Election speeches of Nawaz Sharif is clearly HUMAN metaphor and WAR metaphor. The entailment effect of these metaphors are; to personalize *Pakistan* to manipulate and to trigger the emotions of public. The conceptual metaphors are not single words but phrases that emotionally appeals to the audience in one way or the other. Additionally, in political talks these METAPHORS uncover three fundamental entailment effects: "Simplification", "Persuasion" and "Manipulation". It is likewise conceivable to consider the examination that the source domain of these metaphorical representations are firmly connected with the day today life and the experience of the people, making dynamic political talks reasonable and understandable to the public, so together they assume a remarkable, consequential and powerful role to arouse the emotional responses.

References

- Al-Harashsheh, Ahmad. (2013). The Translatability of Figures of Speech in Khalid Mashaal's Political Speeches: A Critical Discourse Analysis. *International Journal of English Linguistics*; 3(3), 100-114.
- Bougher, L. D. (2012). The Case for Metaphor in Political Reasoning and Cognition. *Bread, Political Psychology*. Princeton University; 33(1), 145-163
- Cen, X. (2009) *The Translation of Political Documents Guided by Cooperative Principles*. Foreign language forum.
- Charteris-Black, J. (2005), *Politicians and Rhetoric*, Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan. Chilton, P. (2004), *Analysing Political Discourse*, London and New York: Routledge.
- Dittmer, Lowell (1977). Political Culture and Political Symbolism: *Toward a Theoretical Synthesis*. *World Politics* 29 (4): 552-83.
- Edelman, M. (1977) *Political Language: Words that succeed and policies that fail*. New York: Academic Press.
- Edelman, M. (1964). *The symbolic uses of politics*. Urbana: University of Illinois Press.

- Fairclough, N. (1989). *Language and power*. London: Longman.
- Ferrari, F (2007). The Metaphor at Work in the Analysis of Political Discourse: Investigating ‘Preventive War’ Persuasion Strategy. *Discourse and Society*, 603-625.
- Greene, Robert. (2003). *The Art of Seduction*. New York: Penguin Books.
- Grey, William (2000). *Metaphor and Meaning*. Retrieved August 10, 2018, from <http://www.ul.ie/~philos/vol4/metaphor.html>.
- Hellsten, L. (2002). *The Politics of Metaphor*. Tampere: Tampere University Press.
- Hu, Y.Y. (2001) Rhetoric in Politics and Its Knowledge Spreading. *Journal of He Nan University* (social science edition 5).
- Kittay, Eva (1987). *Metaphor: Its Cognitive Force and Linguistic Structure*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Kovecses, Z. (2002). *Metaphore, A Practical Introduction*. Oxford University Press.
- Lakoff, G., and Johnson, M. (1980) *Metaphors We Live By*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.
- Lakoff, G. (1991), The Metaphor System Used to Justify War in the Gulf. *Journal of Urban and Cultural Studies* 2(1), 59-72.
- Lakoff, G. (2002). *Moral Politics. How Liberals and Conservatives Think*, Chicago, London: University of Chicago Press.
- Lakoff, G. (2008). *The Political Mind: Why You Can’t Understand 21st-Century American Politics with an 18th-Century Brain*, New York: Penguin Group.
- Lakoff, George. (2004). *Don't think of an elephant! : know your values and frame the debate: the essential guide for progressives*. New York: Chelsea Green.
- Mehdi. 2012. Pakistan: *Politics of rhetoric*. Retrieved August 2018, from www.opinion-maker.org
- Mio, Jeffrey Scott. (1997). *Metaphor and Politics*. California State Polytechnic University, Pomona;12 (2): 113-133.
- Mio, J. (1996), Metaphor, Politics and Persuasion. *Metaphor: Implications and Applications*, Mahwah: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, 127–147.
- Thompson, S. (1996). Politics without metaphors is like a fish without water. In J. S. Mio & A. N. Katz (Eds.), *Metaphor: Implications and applications* (pp. 185-201). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Umar, L., and Rasul, S. (2017), Critical Metaphor Analysis: Nawaz Sharif and the Myth of a Golden Time. *NUML Journal of Critical Inquiry*, Vol.15.
- Van Dijk, T. (1997). *Discourse as Structure and Process*. London / Thousand Oaks / New Delhi
- Wilson, John. (1990) *Politically Speaking*. Oxford: Basil Blackwell, Print.
- Yu N (2008). Metaphor from body and culture. In W. Raymond and Jr. Gibbs (Eds.) *Metaphor and Thought*. London: Cambridge University Press.

Internet Resources:

- Nawaz Sharif May 4, 2018 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SssUjdQFZVY&t=622s> (Accessed Nov 10, 2021)
- Nawaz Sharif April 30, 2018 <http://neonetwork.pk> (Accessed Nov 5, 2021)
- Nawaz Sharif May 14, 2018 <http://neonetwork.pk> (Accessed Nov 15, 2021)
- Nawaz Sharif April 28, 2018 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0t06xHDzRrY> (Accessed Jan 6, 2022)
- Nawaz Sharif April 28, 2018 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=klwkYoZobD8> (Accessed Jan 15, 2022) - Express News.
- Nawaz Sharif July 16, 2018 <https://www.firstpost.com/world/nawaz-sharif-campaigns-for-pml-n-from-jail-asks-pakistanis-> (Accessed Jan 26, 2022)
- <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2017/jul/28/nawaz-sharif-pakistan-colossal-political-corruption-survives> (Accessed Feb 2, 2022)
- “Nawaz Sharif’s party gets majority in Pakistan Parliament”. *The Time of India*. 19 May 2013. Retrieved 4 Feb, 2022.

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